

REFLECTIVE LEARNING RESOURCE MATERIAL AND THE MATHEMATICS LEARNING OUTCOME OF GRADE 9 STUDENTS

HERBERT I. AQUINO

DELON A. CHING

herbert.aquino@deped.gov.ph¹

delon.ching@lspu.edu.ph²

0000-0002-0323-9098¹

0000-0003-1435-4371²

Callejon National High School, Callejon, San Antonio, Quezon, Philippines¹

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

Students' high achievement in Mathematics is one of the main concerns of every Mathematics teacher. Using different learning strategies is necessary to help learners address their difficulties in Mathematical skills to fully understand the lesson. And also, lack of organized schooling and actual teaching-learning processes within the classroom affects students' scholastic achievement. To address, the researcher felt compelled to undertake this research to resolve the gaps found in the performance learning outcome in Mathematics 9 this study on Reflective Learning Resource Material and Mathematics Learning Outcome of Grade 9 Students aimed to determine the impact of the developed learning resource material in the mathematics learning outcome of the learners in terms of analysis, representation and problem-solving skills. The study used a descriptive research design utilizing the pretest/posttest assessment and survey questionnaire as the main instruments which led to achieving its objectives with 35 Grade 9 students as respondents of the school year 2020-2021. The result of the study revealed that reflective learning resource material is highly effective in improving the mathematics learning outcome of the students. Further, findings resulted in a significant difference and an increase in the mathematics learning outcome assessment on analysis, representation, and problem-solving skills which imply that the use of reflective learning resource material helped the students to improve their Mathematics learning outcome. This indicates that from approaching proficiency in analysis skills, representation from developing and proficiency level, and development in problem-solving skills, the learners were able to reach advanced and proficient levels, indicating mastery of the competencies. In certain ways, this demonstrates that the student's reflection in the use of RLRM has a good significant relationship with their mathematics learning outcome. This result suggests that incorporating reflective learning resource material into students' learning activities improved their Mathematics learning outcome.

Keywords: Reflective Learning Resource Material, Mathematics Learning Outcome, Analysis, Representation, and Problem-Solving Skills